

Rochester Regional Physician Assistant Association Continuing Medical Education Conference Abstracts Collection

Spring Refresh: Updates in Medicine

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Table of Contents

1. CARE OF NEWLY ADMITTED ADULT PATIENTS WITH CIRRHOSIS: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT - Renata Lizak, Natalie Dixon
2. ADVANCED PRACTICE PROVIDER PROFESSIONAL BILLING OPTIMIZATION INITIATIVE - Chelsey Donals PA-C, Kelsey Pinkerton PA-C, Hassan Rao MD
3. SUBARACHNOID AND INTRACRANIAL HEMORRHAGE FOLLOWING TENECTEPLASE ADMINISTRATION IN ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE: A CASE STUDY - Gabrielle Blaszczyk PA-C, MS
4. A CASE REPORT OF NON-TRAUMATIC ACUTE COMPARTMENT SYNDROME OF ALL 4 EXTREMITIES SECONDARY TO MYXEDEMA COMA - Michael Boland, PA-C, Brenton LaRiccia, PA-C, Nicholas Bedrin, MD
5. UNDIFFERENTIATED SHOCK IN THE ICU: CASE REPORT - Mira Bella Sirianni, PA-C
6. SEVERE TBI AND PENTOBARBITAL COMA - Yoni Leiderman, PA-C
7. A RARE CAUSE OF TOXIC SHOCK SYNDROME: A CASE REPORT - Sarah Alwardt, PA-C, Vincent E. DeRienzo, PA-C
8. ADVANCED PRACTICE PROVIDER FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM IN CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE RETENTION DATA - Kari Schenck, PA-C, Vincent E. DeRienzo, PA-C, Brenton LaRiccia PA-S

CARE OF NEWLY ADMITTED ADULT PATIENTS WITH CIRRHOSIS: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

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Abstract

- **Background:** Adherence to clinical practice guidelines (CPG) by Advanced Practice Providers (APPs) is crucial for improving patient outcomes that align with national standards, such as those that come from the American Academy for the Study of Liver Disease. This project aimed to assess APP adherence to a newly developed CPG for managing newly admitted patients with cirrhosis.
- **Methods:** A quality improvement project used a convenience sample of hospital medicine APPs and patients admitted to a hepatology co-management service. The intervention included targeted education, rounding, and chart review to assess adherence to the CPG over time. Over five weeks, pre- and post- intervention surveys were administered to APPs. Data and results from surveys and chart review were analyzed for the intervention's effectiveness.
- **Results:** Twenty- three APPs completed the pre-knowledge survey, eight completed the post-knowledge survey. Knowledge of the guideline increased from 8% to 88%. Chart review of six patients showed increased compliance in ordering coagulation studies from 40% in week one to 100% by week three.
- **Conclusion and Implications:** Enhancing APP knowledge of CPGs is feasible and may reduce the overall complications and complexities of those with cirrhosis. Improved adherence promoted consistent care and better patient outcomes. The CPG was integrated as a permanent policy within the institution and will be reviewed annually. Future plans include expanding guideline use to the emergency department, and surgical intensive care unit, along with regular feedback to improve application.

Keywords: cirrhosis, clinical practice guidelines

ADVANCED PRACTICE PROVIDER PROFESSIONAL BILLING OPTIMIZATION INITIATIVE

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Abstract

- Purpose: Advanced Practice Providers (APP) play a vital role in direct patient care, including performing history and physicals, assessing critically ill patients, and engaging in goals of care discussions. The purpose of the APP Professional Billing Optimization Initiative is to augment professional billing education to financially capture this work.
- Description: The aim of this project was to increase total work relative value units (wRVU) by 30% for the Hospital Inpatient Department of Medicine APP group by comparing Quarter 1 2023 to Quarter 1 2024. Multimodal educational tools were created by the team to form the APP Billing Education Series. This included a formal education session presented by a clinician to individuals or small groups, containing basic, need-to-know information, allowing for education to be tailored to specific job requirements. The Education Series also included a laminated quick reference guide and an informal check-in 2 to 4 weeks post formal education to assess for retention and allow for questions to specific cases in real time. The data was collected for total wRVUs as well as individual wRVUs for admissions, critical care and advance care planning comparing pre and post billing education.
- Results: APP total wRVUs increased by 37%. When evaluating only wRVUs pertaining to the education series (admissions, critical care and advanced care planning), the total wRVUs increased by 52%. Admission wRVUs increased by 28%, critical care wRVUs increased by 694%, and advanced care planning wRVUs increased by 1487%. The process measures ensured that hospital census was similar during the time frames evaluated. Average daily hospital census in Quarter 1 2023 was 231 patients and 236 in Quarter 1 2024. The balancing measure ensured that with an increase in APP billing, the medicine physician total wRVU did not inversely decline. Total physician wRVU was 5,700 in Quarter 1 2023 and 5,812 in Quarter 1 2024.
- Conclusions: With the implementation of the APP Billing Education Series, the target goal of increasing total wRVUs by 30% was exceeded. Based on historical payment per wRVU, the estimated impact on revenue would be over \$100,000 annually for the Hospital Medicine APP group. This research has shown that multi-step education is an effective education method. Looking forward, expansion of this model to other departments and roles could also increase the yield of this project. To have a sustainable impact, feedback loops, such as auditing and reviewing charges with individual APPs at regular intervals may be necessary for professional billing to become a mainstay in expected workflow. In addition, continued evaluation of this data could provide justification for added performance-based incentives for APPs. Financially capturing the effort of current practices could result in a considerable shift in APP value, both fiscally and in job satisfaction.

Keywords: In-patient, billing, advanced practice provider workforce

SUBARACHNOID AND INTRACRANIAL HEMORRHAGE FOLLOWING TENECTEPLASE ADMINISTRATION IN ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

- Introduction: Current guidelines recommend Tenecteplase administration within 4.5 hours of last known well time in patients with acute ischemic stroke. However, the risk of hemorrhagic transformation following thrombolysis is a significant concern and requires early identification and management to improve patient outcomes.
- Case Description: A 71-year-old female with a history of cryptogenic stroke (right motor gyrus and left occipital lobe) presented as a code large vessel occlusion via mobile stroke unit. Initial National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale of 8. Contrast tomography confirmed right middle cerebral artery occlusion, and intravenous Tenecteplase was administered. Upon arrival at the emergency department, the patient experienced worsening mental status and emesis, prompting a repeat contrast tomography that revealed intraventricular and subarachnoid hemorrhages. Contrast angiography revealed a suspected rupture of a supraclinoid internal carotid artery aneurysm.
- Discussion: Cerebral aneurysms can develop in patients with hypertension, tobacco use disorder, and family history with personal prior stroke history due to weakened vessel wall integrity. Cerebral aneurysms are often found incidentally but can contribute to complications, as in this patient's case. The supraclinoid aneurysm is likely the cause of her hemorrhagic transformation. Hemorrhagic transformation is crucial to monitor to prevent increased morbidity and mortality. This case study creates a new discussion regarding follow-up imaging in patients with prior strokes to monitor the population at risk of aneurysmal development.

Keywords: Case report, tenecteplase, infundibulum, subarachnoid hemorrhage

A CASE REPORT OF NON-TRAUMATIC ACUTE COMPARTMENT SYNDROME OF ALL 4 EXTREMITIES SECONDARY TO MYXEDEMA COMA

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Abstract

- Acute compartment syndrome (ACS) is a rare but potentially fatal sequelae of myxedema coma. This case report highlights the presentation and management of a patient who developed ACS in all 4 extremities from severe hypothyroidism, which appears to have only been documented once before in the medical literature. Although this case may represent an exceptional presentation of myxedema coma, it highlights

the potentially life threatening complications from hypothyroidism and its improper treatment.

Keywords: Case reports, myxedema coma, compartment syndrome

UNDIFFERENTIATED SHOCK IN THE ICU: CASE REPORT

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Abstract

- Introduction: Shock, a life-threatening manifestation of circulatory failure, is commonly encountered in the ICU. If left untreated, shock progresses to multi-organ failure, resulting in death. Identifying the cause of shock, which may be multi-factorial, is critical to patient survival.
- Description: A 55-year-old male presented to the emergency department via EMS after he was found unresponsive. According to the report provided by EMS, the patient's friend indicated that the patient had been falling and having seizures at home for a week. The friend also stated that the patient quit drinking alcohol 6 days prior and was self-medicating with unspecified illicit substances to manage the withdrawal symptoms. During EMS response, the patient had several seizures and was subsequently intubated in the ED. Workup was significant for elevated troponin, lactate, and BNP. His echocardiogram showed RV dysfunction. Lower extremity dopplers and a chest CT angiography were negative for DVT. His hospital course was complicated by metabolic acidosis, hypotension requiring vasopressors, hypoxemic respiratory failure, and oliguria. The patient's history, labs, and imaging supported the conclusion that the patient's shock had multiple causes. The patient was treated with sedation, mechanical ventilation, anti-epileptics, steroids, antibiotics, and vasopressors. After multiple days of treatment, the patient was extubated and discharged from the ICU to the floor.
- Discussion: Recognition of shock is crucial to prevent further progression of organ failure. Once shock has been identified, the critical next step is to determine the etiology. It is important to consider that etiology may be multi-factorial.

Keywords: Case reports, undifferentiated shock, sepsis

SEVERE TBI AND PENTOBARBITAL COMA

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Abstract

- 21-year-old male presented as a level 1 trauma with a GCS of 3 after he was an unhelmeted motorcyclist struck by a vehicle. He was admitted to the Burn/Trauma ICU for management of his diffuse brain bleeds and cerebral edema secondary to severe TBI, open right tibial/fibular fracture, and acute respiratory failure. The principal focus of management of severe TBI is to limit worsening secondary brain injury which can lead to increased intracranial pressure (ICP), neuronal cell death, and impending cerebral herniation. Optimization of the cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP) is dependent on lowering the ICP while maintaining an adequate mean arterial pressure (MAP). Initial therapies to lower the ICP should include optimization of venous drainage from the brain, adequate sedation and analgesia, osmotic therapies, and paralysis with neuromuscular blockade agents. Pentobarbital is used as last-line therapy for refractory ICP elevation due to its long half-life and side effects such as significant immunosuppression, decreased GI motility, and total loss of neurological function at higher dosages. The patient's hospital course was complicated by refractory ICP elevation, prompting initiation of a medically induced coma with pentobarbital, nonoperative management of his orthopedic injuries, development of severe ARDS secondary to staphylococcus aureus pneumonia, and ultimately a fatal cardiac arrest.

Keywords: Case reports, traumatic brain injury, pentobarbital

A RARE CAUSE OF TOXIC SHOCK SYNDROME: A CASE REPORT

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Abstract

- Introduction: Toxic Shock Syndrome (TSS) is a lethal but treatable condition making early diagnosis critical.). Most cases of *Staphylococcus* associated TSS are methicillin-susceptible and produce exotoxins which results in massive cytokine production. Rhinotillexomania (or compulsive nose picking) is classified as body-focused-repetitive behavior (BFRB) disorder by the DSM-V.
- Case: The following case follows a 38 year old male with *Methicillin-susceptible Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA bacteremia) and TSS as a result of his Rhinotillexomania, and the associated complications from his critical illness. Originally

admitted with profound shock he required empiric, broad-spectrum antimicrobial coverage. Despite this, he clinically worsened and developed acute renal failure and severe acidemia. This caused severe hyperkalemia and polymorphic ventricular tachycardia and subsequent cardiac arrest. After resuscitation and extubation, further history was elicited and revealed a recent worsening of his Rhinotillexomania with new use of a long, sharp, metallic object, described as an ice pick by the patient. Further imaging revealed a severe sinusitis as his source of infection.

- Discussion: About one third of all people carry *Staphylococcus aureus* in the nose. That number is higher for those that pick their nose, and the repeat trauma to the nasal mucosal is a risk factor for developing methicillin resistance and colonization.

Keywords: Case reports, toxic shock syndrome, rhinotillexomania

ADVANCED PRACTICE PROVIDER FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM IN CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE RETENTION DATA

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Abstract

- Background/Aim: Post-pandemic ICU bed expansion in ICU censuses has led to the increased demand for critical care advanced practice providers (APPs). Critical care patients carry an inherently increased risk of adverse events due to the nature of their disease process. The combination of high risk, complex disease, and provider inexperience, increases the variability in the clinical decisions made and subsequent risk of adverse events within the critical care setting. APPs in critical care rely on post-graduate training to hone their clinical and procedural skills to provide care to patients at the highest scope of APP practice. This is in contrast to unit candidates hired directly to a specific unit and undergoing a traditional six month orientation process. This study looks to evaluate APP retention rates at one academic medical center at relevant intervals and to investigate for the presence of differences in graduates of said post-graduate training program versus traditional orientees.
- Methods: Human resources and program data were compiled. Descriptive statistics were utilized to display retention rates for newly employed adult critical care providers at 6 month, 1 year, and 2 year intervals.
- Results: We found no difference in retention rates at six and twelve months. However, a significant difference was found at the 24 month period. This suggests that at our institution, an initial investment in a twelve month post-graduate training program for APP's results in more APP's staying employed in adult critical care services after 24 months than traditional orientees.

Keywords: Post-graduate training, advanced practice provider workforce, retention